

DISCUSSING AND IDENTIFYING SPORTS REQUIREMENTS OF CLIENTS OF SPORTS FACILITIES OF KURDISTAN PROVINCE FROM THE VIEW OF YOUTHS

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Abstract:

The aim of the present research was to discuss and identify the sports related requirements and needs of clients of Kurdistan province's sports facilities from the view of youths. In terms of purpose, it's considered as an applied research and also in terms of strategy, it is considered as a descriptive-survey study which is carried out under field methods. In order to elaborate on the goals of this study, a researcher made questionnaire including 30 items and arranged based on a five degrees Likert scale was employed. The validity of the questionnaire was approved by certain experts of physical education and management and also its reliability was calculated as 0.78 through the application of Kronbach's alpha method. The population of this study includes the entire 15-24 year old boys and girls throughout the province of Kurdistan. Among the population, a number of 384 individuals were selected as the sample through the application of Morgan's table, however 450 questionnaires were distributed among the sample and ultimately, 391 questionnaires were collected back as completed questionnaires. For the purpose of sampling, a cluster sampling method was employed. In addition, for analysis of data at descriptive level, the abundance tables, abundance percentages, mean and standard deviation methods were used and for the same purpose at inferential level, the tests of Kolmogorov-Smirnoff, one sample t and Freedman were employed which were all performed by the software of SPSS v.22. Obtained results indicated that there exists a significant difference between sports priorities and sports related needs of clients of Kurdistan province's sports facilities. In addition, the status of Kurdistan province's sports facilities was significantly unsuitable.

There was also a significant difference noticed between the sports related needs of male and female clients of Kurdistan province's sports facilities.

Keywords: sports need, sports facility, needs assessment, Kurdistan province

Introduction

More than two thousand years ago, regarding human's need for continuous activity; Hippocrates, a Greek physician has declared that having continuous activity is necessary for human health and that as a result of having this continuous physical activity different organs of the human body will all remain their health, gain strength and also their aging process slows down. If mankind's lives get distant from movement activities, then the organs of the body will lose their agility and become susceptible to different diseases and also their growth rate declines and instead their aging process accelerates (Deborah and Butcher, 2006). At the current era, mechanization of modern life and reduced physical movement among the entire communities, have led to occurrence of several problems due to movement poverty. Nowadays, more than any time before, the necessity of performance of regular physical activities is felt for maintaining the health of the human mind and body. Basically, development of sports is related to increased participation and propagation of opportunities and advantages of making presence at sports activities. Participation in sports and physical activities makes connection between a wide range of concepts including presence of children in games, participation of women in sports, presence of youths in regular sports and ultimately development of public sports and professional sports (Kaliopé et al. 2008).

The solution for freedom from movement poverty which is due to mechanization of today's modern life is to perform sports activities. At the current era, exercising is considered as a way through which people can overcome their mental and nervous stresses. In comparison to inactive people, people who exercise regularly are less exposed to occurrence of heart attacks and their brains also have more time to rest. In addition, during resting, their heartbeat rate decreases, they feel more confidence; they are more optimistic and are less prone development of depression. Therefore, with respect to the importance of presence of all people in sports activities and benefitting from positive effects of exercising including positive mental, physical, social and economic effects; has forced governments to plan for and invest on sports and healthy recreations (Momtazbakhsh and Fakoor, 2008).

At the current era, sport is considered as a social phenomenon which is known as a need in every human society and is also highly prioritized as a cultural phenomenon

(Evington and Edgerton, 2012). Human's life in past times forced them to put efforts, carry heavy weights, perform hard activities and farm and construct by hands or simple tools. All these activities engaged a large number or a number of body parts and as a result of a suitable blood flow and suitable breathing, their muscles became tough and therefore, they were ready for any other hard activities (Deborah and Bucher, 2006).

Previous studies regarding the effects of sports activities on mental and physical health, life-span, liveliness, improved social relations and enrichment of free-times have imposed an increase on people's participation in different sports especially in different fields of public sports. For this reason, nowadays, most advanced and developed countries are challenging each other in terms of planning and organizing the public sports of their country. These effects are important to the extent that currently, in developed countries sports and healthy recreations are considered as an important industry and an effective factor on growth of national economy. For example, the income of this industry in the United States of America during the year 2000 was close to 350.000.000.000 dollars. It is obvious that any country which gets left behind from this increasing trend, will not be able to fill the gap in any way and therefore, ultimately the differences in terms of benefiting from the effects of sports and movement activities will be more tangible (Kaliopé et al. 2008).

Since public sports is considered as a principal element for the health of members of a community, the necessity for its development is felt more than any time before. In this regard, authorities and related organizations and institutes should not consider public sports as an extra expense; rather they should view it as an investment on personal and public health as well as social benefits which provide certain economic sources (Deborah and Bucher, 2006). In addition, for having a suitable and proper planning in this context, managers need to assess the needs of citizens, also they should comprehend the relation between sports related needs of clients of sports facilities, and the existing (and future) sports facilities. Carlson (2000) believes that need assessment is a systematic process for determining the needs and discovers a gap between the current situations and required situations. Considering these content, it can be declared that if planning for sports is done according to need assessment researches, then the probability of obtaining the goals of programs increases.

Several researches have been performed on different societies in this context. Most of these researches have elaborated on the manner of passing free times by people and the barriers of participation in public sports. In fact, these researches have not paid much attention to sports related needs of people. In this regard, it can be referred to the researches performed by Afarinesh Khaki et al. (2006), Azizi et al. (2012), Ramezanejad et al. (2010), and Ghafoori et al. (2004) and etc. all of the aforementioned

researches have elaborated on discussing and comparing the views of different societies regarding the methods of development of sports or discussing the incentives of participators in sports activities. Only a few researches have discussed the sports related needs and requirements of people and as examples its can be referred to the researches performed by Davoodi et al. (2015) and Varmaghani (2013). Davoodi et al. (2015) performed a research, determined the sports and recreational needs of students, and compared them with programs offered at State universities of Tehran city.

They concluded that there existed a significant difference between the offered programs at universities and requirements and needs of students. Also, a significant difference was witnessed between facilities of different sports for girls and boys. Therefore, it can be stated that the existing facilities of the aforementioned universities were unable to fulfill the needs of students regarding the context of sports and recreation. On the other hand, results of research have shown that gender plays a crucial role in determining the presence and participation of students in sports activities. In this regard, it was made clear that males have a higher passion and interest for participating in sports and recreational activities compared to females. On the other hand, Varmaghani (2013) has performed a research titled as assessment of sports needs of firefighters of Tehran. He performed his research with a managerial approach on the entire firefighters of the city of Tehran during 2012 and concluded that sports requirements and needs of firefighters are respectively swimming, physical fitness, volleyball, mountain climbing, futsal, football, chess, ping pong, running and body building. In terms of facilitation needs, also their needs were prioritized as multipurpose saloons and pools. Among the obtained goals of participation in sports activities, it can be referred to counts such as feeling of liveliness, reduced stress and anxiety while facing accidents and improved job efficiency. In addition, the solutions for improvement of motivation for participation is sports activities included counts such as holding recreational trips, performance of sports activities along with families, holding educational-sports courses and holding regular sport competitions. Lack of an experienced coach, unsuitability of costs, exhaustion due to sports activities, and lack of sufficient time, lack of facilities and equipment and lacking a company for exercising were respectively considered as barriers of participation in sports activities.

With respect to the fact that until now, there had been no extensive researches performed in the context of assessment of needs and codification of a social-sports data bank in Iran, it seems necessary to elaborate on the problems of sports and assessment of people's views, especially the youths' views regarding sports, level of participation in sports and etc. so that the aforementioned problems are recognized and therefore a more suitable approach is adopted for eliminating and overcoming them. As a talented

province in terms of sports, the province of Kurdistan also lacks a general program for development of sports and it lacks suitable sports facilitation according to needs of the society and therefore its sports capita is very low.

On this basis, the researcher of the present study has tried to provide an answer for the question: What are the sports needs of clients of Kurdistan province's sports facilities from the viewpoint of youths?

Methods

With respect to the aim of this research which is to discuss and identify the sports related needs of clients of Kurdistan province's sports facilities from the view of youths, this study is considered as an applied research and also in terms of method it is a descriptive survey study which was carried out under field methods.

The research population includes the entire young boys and girls of Kurdistan province who aged between 15 and 24 years. According to the data obtained from the Kurdistan's statistics center, they are 305002 individuals consisted of 146683 boys and 158319 girls. Through the application of the Morgan table, the sample size as determined as 384 individuals, however ultimately a number of 391 completed questionnaires were collected. In addition, for the purpose of sampling, the cluster sampling method was employed for the cities of Marivan, Sanandaj, Dehgalan, Gharveh, Saghez, Divandarreh, Bijar and Sarvabad. After selecting the sample cities through a simple random sampling method, the clients of sports facilities were also selected through a simple random sampling method.

The instruments applied in this research include a researcher made questionnaire. For this purpose, 11 experts of sports management field and sociology were asked to give their ideas regarding the content and face validities of the aforementioned questionnaire. The final questionnaire included 30 items which were based on five degrees Likert scale. In addition, in order to test the reliability of the questionnaire, the Kronbach's alpha method was employed and for this purpose, the questionnaires were first distributed among a forty individual sample. The Kronbach's alpha coefficient calculated for this sample was 0.78.

For analysis of data at descriptive level, the methods abundance table, abundance percentage, mean and standard deviation employed and also for the purpose of analysis at inferential levels, first the Kolmogorov-Smirnoff test was applied for testing the normality of data distribution and next, the one sample t-test was applied for comparing the sample mean with presumed society mean. After this, the Freedman test was undertaken for prioritization of sports activities and sports related needs of

clients of sports facilities. The entire statistical operations were completed via the SPSS v.22.0 software.

Results

Demographic data obtained regarding the studied subjects in this research indicate that 48% of the sample was consisted of females and 52% was also consisted of females. In addition, 60.3% of the total population was single and 39.7% were married. The mode of the society is populated with youths who hold a B.A degree with a 26.7% share; this was while only 1.5% of the sample was undereducated. Additionally, in terms of age, the most observed abundance was associated with the age group of 18-20 years with a 36.5% total share. Respectively the lowest abundance was associated with +23 years age group with a total share of 12%. Among the findings related to description of research variables, it was observed that the highest mean was related to sports facilities and the lowest was related to suitable use of sports facilities.

Results of the K-S test indicated that the entire distributions were statistically normal (table 3); therefore parametric statistical tests were selected for analysis of data.

Table 1: Statistics of Kolmogorov-Smirnoff test

Distribution	Statistics		Research variables
	z	p	
Prioritization of activities	1.19	0.11	normal
Status of sports facilities	0.86	0.46	normal
Suitable use of sports facilities	1.19	0.12	normal

The Freedman test was applied for prioritization of sports activities from the view of clients of sports facilities throughout the province of Kurdistan. The results have indicated that there exists a significant difference between sports activities of clients of Kurdistan province's sports facilities; in a way that the highest priority was occupied by Futsal while the lowest being occupied by ping pong (Table 2).

Table 2: Results of Freedman test

Number	391
Chi-do	121.07
Freedom degree	9
Significance	0.001

Table 3: Prioritization of sports activities from the view of clients of Kurdistan Province sports facilities

Activity	Average score
Futsal	7.04
Volleyball	6.83
Body building	6.53
Other sports	6.39
Badminton	5.71
Basketball	5.55
Wrestling	5.43
Jogging	5.19
Ping pong	4.87

Considering the normality of data distributions, the one sample t-test was used for discussing the status of sports facilities and results have indicated that the status of Kurdistan Province's sports facilities is significantly unsuitable, since the observed mean was lower than the expected statistical mean and the statistic of t was also negative (Table 4).

Table 4: Results of the one sample t test

Variable	Mean	F.D	Statistical mean	t	Sig.
Suitability of sports facilities according to the requirements of clients	2.87	3	399	-12.23	0.01

The Freedman test was applied for prioritization of sports related requirements from the view of clients of sports facilities throughout the province of Kurdistan. The results have indicated that there exists a significant difference between sports related requirements of clients of Kurdistan province's sports facilities (table, 5); in a way that the highest priority was occupied by swimming while the lowest being occupied by ping pong (table 6).

Table 5: Results of Freedman test

Number	391
Chi-do	132.54
Freedom degree	9
Significance	0.001

Table 6: Prioritization of sports related requirements from the view of clients of
Kurdistan Province sports facilities

Activity	Average score
Swimming	8.01
Aerobics	7.71
Volleyball	7.21
Body building	7.08
Yoga	6.92
Badminton	6.72
Other sports	6.31

The Chi-Do test was performed for making a comparison between the priorities of sports requirements from the view of females and the priorities from the view of males. Results indicated that there existed a difference between the former and the latter. The first and second priorities of females were occupied by Aerobics and Yoga while, the priorities from the view of males were occupied by swimming and body building as the first and second priorities in terms of sports related requirements (table, 7).

Table 7: Abundance distribution and percentage according to sports related needs of
females and males

Sig.	Chi-2	Females			Males				
		3 rd priority	2 nd priority	1 st priority	3 rd priority	2 nd priority	1 st priority		
0.05	65.56	30	30	50	1	12	13	Abundance	Aerobics
		8.5	8.5	12.5	0.2	3.0	3.2	Abundance percentage	
		20	39	18	16	35	16	Abundance	Badminton
		4.0	9.8	4.5	4.0	8.8	4.0	Abundance percentage	
		19	7	20	27	10	32	Abundance	Body building
		4.8	1.8	5.0	6.8	4.5	8.0	Abundance percentage	
		19	43	12	17	39	9	Abundance	Volleyball
		4.8	10.8	3.0	4.2	9.8	2.2	Abundance percentage	
30	39	32	48	56	60	Abundance	Swimming		
7.5	9.8	8.0	12.0	14.0	15.0	Abundance percentage			
40	15	28	11	4	6	Abundance	Yoga		
10.0	3.8	7.0	2.8	1.0	1.5	Abundance percentage			
19	14	7	34	15	11	Abundance	Handball		
4.8	3.5	1.8	8.5	3.8	2.8	Abundance percentage			
11	10	15	11	9	20	Abundance	Ping pong		
2.8	2.5	3.8	2.8	2.2	4.0	Abundance percentage			

Discussion and Conclusions

Results have indicated that a significant difference exists between the sports activities of clients of sports facilities of Kurdistan Province; in a way that the highest priority is occupied by Futsal and the lowest priority is occupied by Ping pong. The obtained results are consistent with parts of the results of the research carried out by Davoodi et al (2016) and Holzweher (2002). The reason for this consistency could be assumed to be related to physical, psychological and other characteristics. In fact no single field of sports is ever able to attract the entire people of a society towards itself because people have different ideals and interests. As an explanation for this result it can be stated that need is itself a multidimensional concept and its' full comprehension largely depends on sociology.

Among different definitions, the most complete and accepted upon definition is to consider need as a type of gap analysis which expresses the gap between the current statuses and ideal statuses. In fact when need is expressed, every individual can have his or her special and specific needs which might be different from others' need. Also in terms of sports related requirements and needs, the same definition could be applied. Considering the vast development and variability of sports fields, it can be expected to observe a significant difference among the interesting fields of sports for each individual. Several issues are known as contributors to this phenomenon. For example, one of the variables which can be effective on individuals' interest in a certain field of sports can be age. Usually, people at younger ages are looking for more challenges and are therefore interested in more active sports while people at older ages are usually the fans of sports with least amount of physical engagement.

In addition to age and physical conditions, it should also be taken into account that people have also different personalities and each individual has his or her own specific interests. Therefore, the entire people in a certain age group cannot be expected to be interested in a similar field of sports. For an instance, some people are interested in sports fields which require more physical engagement while some might be interested in sports with minimum amounts of physical engagement. Or even some might be interested in team and co-op sports while some might be interested in singular sports. Therefore, it seems rational to observe a difference between the priorities of clients of sports facilities. Nevertheless, the results of this research have shown that the status of Kurdistan province's sports facilities is significantly unsuitable. In this regard, the observed mean was less than the expected statistical mean and also the t statistic was negative.

The obtained results are in consistence with the results of researches performed by Davoodi et al. (2015) and Red and Phillips (2005). Red and Philips (2005) concluded that intensity, duration and frequency of physical activity are significantly related to the quality of sports equipment. In addition, closeness of the sports facility is effective on the physical activity of clients. It seems that lack of a sports related need assessment has caused the similarity between the results of the aforementioned research and the present study. A ports facility is a place in which athletes exercise and perform other sports activities. Therefore, suitability of these places for satisfaction of clients is highly important.

Sports facilities provide suitable opportunities for growth of emotions, cognition, perception and sociality for every class of the society. Providing security for the clients of sports facilities is one of the most important tasks of managers of such places. Several different contexts exist in a sports facility which might be taken into consideration. One of these contexts is equipment. In fact, sports facilities are way more than just a sports activity place. In addition to creation of a sports facility, if we want to assess it, we should also consider the quality of the equipment. A sports facility may be very large and spacious but at the same time lack qualified equipment. This kind of facility will be assessed s an unsuitable facility. Additionally, the issues related to the safety of sports facilities are of significant importance. In fact, security is considered as an assessment factor of sports facilities. If a sports facility is observed as an unsuitable facility in terms of safety and security, then it might be totally evaluated as an unsuitable facility. Since if a person feels unsafe in a sports facility, then he or she might stop using the facility, or at least reduce his or her presence at the facility. Now, considering all these interpretations, it can be seen that considering the ideas of clients of Kurdistan province's sports facilities, the sports facilities of this province are in an unsuitable status and therefore, solutions must be sought for in this regard.

In other sections of the research, results have indicates that a significant difference exists between the sports related needs of clients of sports facilities. In this regard, the highest priority was occupied by swimming and the lowest priority was also occupied by ping pong. This result is consistent with the result obtained by Varmaghani (2013). Varmaghani (2013) concluded that swimming and body building were the first priorities of sports related needs of the studied sample. One reason for this consistency can be related to liveliness of swimming and other water sports.

In fact, today water sports have been able to attract several fans which are related to the nature of this sport and its environment. With respect to the first hypothesis, it was stated that different people with respect to variables such as personality, economic status, different states of physical fitness etc. are oriented towards different sports

fields. These people will have activities in a certain field of sports according to their taste and the results of this research have indicated that 255 of the total population of clients have expressed their first priority of sports needs as swimming. With respect to the live nature of swimming and other water sports, it seems rational to observe a difference among people in terms of their interesting field of sport. On the other hand, nowadays also the sports field of Aerobics has been able to attract several fans and because of its many advantages, people are showing great interest for this field of sports. In this regard, it can be stated that media advertisements can have a very deep impact in this trend. Since aerobics is an air intake based sports field and that the researches have shown that aerobics can reduce weight; this sport has gained much popularity among the communities.

Ultimately, results have shown that there exists a significant difference between the sports related needs of females and males, who refer to sports facilities. In this regard, the first and second priorities of girls were aerobics and yoga while the same priorities for boys were occupied with swimming and body building. This obtained result is consistent with parts of the results obtained by Fathi (2010) and Varmaghani (2013). In addition, the results were inconsistent with the results obtained by Atghia (2009) and Davoodi et al. (2015). Fathi (2010) performed a research titled as sociological determination of students' sports participation. He concluded that factors such as marriage status, gender, social base, economic base etc. are in a significantly meaningful relation with sports participation among students. It seems that with respect to including physiological, mental, physical fitness and other characteristics, gender is the main source of difference in type of sports need of individuals. Varmaghani (2013) in his research on firefighters of Tehran concluded that Swimming and bodybuilding were the first priorities from the view of firefighters.

One reason for this consistency may lie in the factor of gender. Since the population of Iran's firefighters is only consisted of men, based on reasons such as improving and maintaining physical capabilities and obtaining body fitness men might be more interested in heavier sports. On the other hand, Atghia (2009) concluded that the priorities of sports needs of women employed in AL Zahra University included general body building, sports related to pain caused by arthritis and osteoporosis, water sports, sports aimed at elimination of muscular pains, training different sports fields and ultimately jogging. One reason for the lack of consistency of the present study and the mentioned research could lie in type of populations. Atghia's (2009) research includes the discussion of sports needs of employed women which in addition to age can add the job of individuals as another effective factor. Employed women are usually interested in sports which can reduce the side effects of their jobs and their daily life

and age related issues. This is while young girls are probably more interested in sports related to general health and body fitness. In addition, Davoodi et al. (2015) have concluded that the needs of the students of state governed universities of the city of Tehran were prioritized as swimming, futsal, football, volleyball and badminton for boys and swimming, badminton, volleyball and mountain hiking for girls. Maybe the difference in sports facilities at disposal of the subjects of these researches have had their impact on the interests of people and caused this lack of consistency.

In fact, despite existence of a significantly meaningful difference between males' and females' needs, also they can have different needs in terms of sports too. With respect to the results of this hypothesis, it can be stated that gender is an important effective factor on individuals' interest in different sports fields and activities. As males and females have different and several differences in terms of physical fitness, it seems also rational to witness a difference among their desirable fields of sports. Usually men are more interested in sports that require more power and physical strengths while women mostly participate in sports which are suitable for their character. On the other hand, also social factors are effective on this issue and in a certain society, some sports fields might be meant for men while some other might be meant and intended for women. Although that it is not true and men and women can equally take part in any sports field they like, but the regulations of the society can affect the choice of individuals. Therefore, it seems rational and logic to witness a difference between the interesting sports from the view of male and females. Nowadays, as a result of intensive advertisements, the sports field of aerobics has gained a significant popularity among women and most women are oriented towards this field of sports with the goal of losing weight. This is while aerobics is in the view of most men, women's sports and they prefer to participate in sports such as body building.

References

1. Atghia, N. (2008). Training needs assessment for women working in the University, and offer practical solutions. *Movement Sciences journal*, the sixth, Volume I, Issue 11, pp. 79-95.
2. Eddington, DC. W., Adgrtvn him. Reggie. (2011). *Biology of Physical Activity*. (Translated by Mohammad Nikbakht). Tehran: Publication of the first edition, Eighth Edition.
3. Afarinesh Khaki, Akbar, Tondnewis, F; Mozaffari, Sayed Ahmad. (2005). Compare the views of faculty members, coaches, athletes and administrators on

- how to develop the sport. *Movement Sciences journal*, Volume 3, Issue 5, pp. 22-1.
4. Davoodi, Karim; Shahlayi, J.; Ghafuri, F. (2015). Comparing the sports and recreational needs of students with extra-curricular activities programs at universities in Tehran. *Sports Management*, Volume 7, Number 4, pp. 513-531.
 5. Deborah, a. West, Charles A. Boucher. (2006). *Principles of Physical Education and Sport*. (Translated by Ahmad free), Tehran: Publication of Study and Compilation of Humanities Books (left), Centre for Research and Development of Human Sciences, 2012.
 6. Ramezanejad, Rahim, Rahmani-Nia, F; Taghavi Takyar, Amir. (2009). Participants in the exercise of universal motivations in open spaces. *Sports Management*, No. 2, pp. 19-5.
 7. Azizi, bisotoon, Jalali Farahani, M.; Khabiri, M. (2011). Attitudes of students living in dormitories of Tehran University on sport. *Sports Management*, No. 8, pp. 91- 75.
 8. Ghafouri, F; Rahmanseresht, Hussein; Kozehchyan, Hashem, Ehsan, Mohammad. (2003). Study of Physical Education professionals' attitudes towards the role of the mass media (radio, television and newspapers) in the championship and the public interest in sports. *HARAKAT*, Issue 16, pp. 57-78.
 9. Fathi, Soroush. (2009). Sociological explanation student sports participation. *Social Science Research*, Issue IV, pp. 145-173.
 10. Momtaz Bakhsh, M; Fakoor, yousef. (2007). Investigating the mechanisms used to promote and develop sport for women Police University. *Quarterly disciplinary knowledge, the ninth year, the second edition*, pp. 53-61.
 11. Vрмаqhany, Majid. (2012). Firefighters in Tehran Sports assessment management approach. Unpublished master's thesis, Tarbiat Modarres University.
 12. Carlson, R. (2000). Ethnic differentiation as a determinant for sport practical pation among children and youth. College of physical Education and sport. University of Stockholm.
 13. Holzweher, F. (2002). *Sport for all as a Social Change and Fitness Development*. Institute of Sport Scenic, Vienna University, Austria.
 14. Kalliopi, S., Shilbury D., Christine, G. (2008). Sport Development Systems, Policies and Pathways: An Introduction to the Special Issue. *Sport Management Review*, Vol. 11, pp. 217-223.
 15. Reed, J. A., and Phillips, D. A. (2005). Relationships Between physical Activity and the proximity of Exercise Facilities and Home Exercise Equipment used by

undergraduate university students. J Am Coll Health. 2005 May-Jun, 53(6):285-90.

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